

A Clinical Study of Iatrogenic Cutaneous Manifestations in Neonates in Intensive Care Unit in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract

Background: Neonatal dermatology includes a wide spectrum of cutaneous issues that show up in a neonate's skin during the initial month of life, ranging from regular phenomena to significantly morbid lesions. This review was done to find out the magnitude of iatrogenic issues so as to minimise and prevent them whenever possible.

Aims and Objectives: To study the prevalence of iatrogenic problems among neonates in neonatal intensive care unit (NICU)

Materials and Methods: In a hospital-based, prospective research conducted between November 2021 and October 2022, 1000 neonates admitted to the tertiary NICU of Silchar Medical College & Hospital were evaluated.

Results: 110 (11%) of the 1000 newborns analyzed had iatrogenic cutaneous diseases. Out of these 110 neonates, 66 (60%) had just one problem, 23 (20.90%) had two, and 21 (19.10%) had three or more disorders going on at once. Preterm neonates (62.72%) were more likely than full-term (34.54%) and post-term (2.72%) neonates to have skin lesions. In terms of iatrogenic injuries, needle prick injuries (76.36%) and adhesive tape injuries (22.72%) were the most frequent. Diaper dermatitis (13.63%), Thermal injuries (10.90%), extravasation injury (2.72%), bronze baby syndrome (4.54%), CPAP injuries (4.54%) and perinatal injuries (3.63%) were manifestations which were commonly noted in low birth weight (LBW) neonates.

Conclusion: A variety of iatrogenic injuries that occur in neonate can cause skin damage. Because of the scarcity of studies, obstetricians, paediatricians, dermatologists and nursing staff are less acquainted with these conditions. As a result, it is important to keep all medical professionals involved in infant care, up to date.

Keywords: Neonatal dermatology, Neonatal intensive care unit, Neonates, Iatrogenic injuries, Iatrogenic cutaneous manifestations

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Introduction

Neonatal dermatology includes a wide spectrum of cutaneous issues that show up in a neonate's skin during the initial month

of life, ranging from regular phenomena to significantly morbid lesions. The skin is the newborns 'interface' with the outside

world. The first four weeks of extra-uterine life are typically considered to be the neonatal phase. The skin of the newborn is essential to the vital processes of mechanical protection, thermoregulation, immunosurveillance, and maintenance of a barrier that prevents unavoidable loss of body fluids. It also plays a crucial role in the transition from the aqueous intrauterine environment to extra-uterine terrestrial life. By definition, neonatal dermatology includes the vast variety of cutaneous conditions that manifest during the first four weeks of life. Neonatal skin has a wide range of abnormalities, from healthy and temporary to blatantly diseased, yet none of them need treatment. Most infant skin lesions are often benign, temporary, and self-limiting. For a variety of reasons, newborns are admitted to the neonatal critical care unit. When some may acquire other cutaneous signs while they are in the newborn critical care unit, some may have dermatological disorders. The Neonatal Intensive Care Unit's (NICU) life-supporting devices, such as fetal scalp electrodes, transcutaneous oxygen monitors, skin temperature monitoring probes, adhesive tapes, and pulse oximeters, can result in significant skin lesions, such as cutaneous puncture marks, scars, or lacerations, as well as complications. Despite the fact that therapeutic operations have decreased morbidity and mortality, there is a high chance that they might cause iatrogenic cutaneous problems. In order to enhance the care of babies, it is necessary to analyze these problems.

The majority of newborn babies admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit were either born preterm, had significant congenital defects, or had birth problems [1].

Neonatal dermatoses fall into several categories [2].

1. Transient skin disorder
2. Congenital and genetic skin disorders
3. Acquired skin disorders
4. Developmental skin disorders

5) Iatrogenic and traumatic skin complications.

Neonatal skin differs from adult skin in that it is lighter, thinner, has weaker intercellular bonds, and secretes less perspiration and sebaceous fluid. Additionally, the detoxification and deactivation of substances administered to newborn skin are less efficient. Both healthy newborns and those requiring hospitalization in neonatal intensive or semi-intensive care units due to a condition have newborn skin lesions rather often. The frequency and severity of skin injury must be lessened, and neonatal care members must be mindful that regular operations might result in long-term morbidity.

Iatrogenic injuries are those that occur to patients unintentionally as a result of receiving medical treatment in some way [3]. Iatrogenic skin conditions can develop prior to labour, during delivery or following delivery [4]. Gestational age, low birth weight, central venous catheters, length of stay in NICU, mechanical ventilation and support with cutaneous positive airway pressure are main risk factors [5].

For resuscitation, a variety of invasive methods may be required, but margin of safety between successful therapy and iatrogenic injury is narrow. Skin can be punctured, sliced, peeled, and burnt either thermally or chemically. The newborn delivered before 32 weeks of gestation has a very thin stratum corneum, thus prone to injury [1].

In our nation, there is a dearth of literature on newborn iatrogenic dermatoses. The goal of the current study was to analyze these diseases in order to comprehend the wide range of skin disorders that afflict newborns and to minimize and avoid them wherever feasible.

Material and Method

A hospital based prospective study was conducted in the Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Silchar (Assam), for one year from November 2021 to October 2022 after approval from ethical committee. A total of

1000 neonates admitted in tertiary setup NICU were examined during the study period.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Only newborns hospitalized to neonatal critical care unit (first four weeks of life).
2. Any skin condition that newborns with admission have or that has acquired while they were in the neonatal intensive care unit.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Neonates/ infants not admitted in neonatal ICU.
2. Neonates suffering from antenatal injuries.

Preterm, term, and post-term neonates were divided into categories based on the stage of pregnancy. It was noted the birth weight. Neonatal systemic illnesses, the manner of birth, the causes of NICU hospitalization,

and other details were also noted. Diagnosis was made on clinical features and photographs of the newbornswere taken. The results were tabulated and statistically analysed.

Results

110 (11%) of the 1000 newborns investigated had iatrogenic cutaneous diseases; 58 (52.72%) of them were males and 52 (47.27%) were girls. Iatrogenic cutaneous lesions were discovered in 58 (52.72%) neonates on the first day of life, 39 (35.45%) over the next 2–7 days, 7 (6.36%) within the next 8–14 days, 5 (4.54%) within the next 22–28 days, and 1 (0.90%) within the next 15–21 days. Out of these 110 neonates, 66 (60%) had just one problem, 23 (20.90%) had two, and 21 (19.10%) had three or more disorders going on at once. Preterm newborns (62.72%) had the most skin lesions, followed by full-term (34.54%) and post-term (2.72%) neonates, shown in Table 1 to 4.

Table 1: Age distribution

Age (in days)	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
1	58	52.72
2-7	39	35.45
8-14	7	6.36
15-21	5	4.54
22-28	1	0.90

Table 2: Distribution of neonates according to number of cutaneous manifestations

Number of cutaneous manifestations	No. of cases	Percentage
One type of lesion	66	60
Two types of lesions	23	20.90
Three and more lesions	21	19.10
Total	110	100

Table 3: Gender distribution

Participants	Total number (n=110)
Males	58 (52.72%)
Females	52 (47.27%)

Table 4: Relationship of skin manifestations with maturity of neonate

Gestational age	Number of neonates (%)
Preterm (<37 weeks)	69 (62.72)
Term (37-42 weeks)	38 (34.54)
Post term (>42 weeks)	3 (2.72)

Among the iatrogenic injuries, needle prick injuries were commonly noted i.e., seen in 84(76.36%) neonates followed by adhesive tape injuries in 25(22.72%) neonates. Diaper dermatitis was seen in 15(13.63%) neonates, thermal injuries in 12(10.90%), extravasation injury in 3(2.72%), bronze baby syndrome in 5(4.54%), CPAP injuries in 5(4.54%) and perinatal injuries in 4(3.63%) neonates were other manifestations which were commonly noted in neonates. Iatrogenic manifestations were common in low birth weight (LBW) neonates i.e., seen in 49(44.55%) neonates. 47(42.73%) neonates had normal birth weight, 13(11.82%) had very low birth weight (VLBW) and 1(0.9%) had extremely low birth weight (ELBW). Most of the neonates i.e., 93(84.54%) were delivered by normal vaginal delivery. 12 (10.90%) neonates were delivered by LSCS (Lower segment caesarean section) and 5(4.54%) were delivered by instrumental delivery, shown in Table 5 to 7 & Figure 1 to 10.

Table 5: Type of iatrogenic manifestations

Manifestation	Total number of cases (%)
Needle prick injuries	84 (76.36%)
Adhesive tape injuries	25(22.72%)
Diaper dermatitis	15(13.63%)
Thermal injuries	12(10.90%)
Extravasation injury	3(2.72%)
Bronze baby syndrome	5(4.54%)
CPAP injuries	5(4.54%)
Perinatal injuries	4(3.63%)

Table 6: Relationship of skin manifestations with birth weight of neonate

Birth weight (kg)	No. of cases	Percentage(%)
<1.0 (ELBW)	1	0.9
1.0-1.49 (VLBW)	13	11.82
1.50-2.49 (LBW)	49	44.55
2.5-4.5 (Normal)	47	42.73
	110	100

Table 7: Relationship of skin manifestations with mode of delivery of neonate

Mode of delivery	No. of cases	Percentage(%)
Normal	93	84.54
LSCS	12	10.90
Instrumental	5	4.54
	110	100

Figure 1: Needle prick injury

Figure 2: Bronze baby syndrome

Figure 3: Miliaria Crystallina

Figure 4: Erythema from removal of adhesives

Figure 5: Chemical burn from Alcohol

Figure 6: Extravasation injury

Figure 7: Pressure necrosis from CPAP

Figure 8: Diaper dermatitis

Figure 9: Laceration following instrumental delivery

Figure 10: Erythema and erosions over face following repeated manipulation in face presentation delivery.

Discussion

In the current study, 110 of the 1000 newborns hospitalized to the neonatal critical care unit exhibited iatrogenic skin abnormalities of one kind or another. Our study found that preterm neonates (62.72%)

were primarily affected, which was consistent with the findings of a study by *Kugelman et al* [6], in which 57% of preterm neonates displayed iatrogenic cutaneous manifestations. There are

significant consequences for illness and survival since the epidermal barrier is inadequately developed in the immature newborns between 23 and 26 weeks of gestation, who are at the limits of viability [7]. The thickness of skin in premature infants is 0.9mm, whereas it is 1.2mm in newborn and 2.1mm in adults. In premature infant, thickness of epidermis is 25-20 micrometre, only 5-6 layers of stratum corneum with glycogen filled spinous cells and immature dermis [8].

In our study, low birth weight babies were affected more commonly. 44.55% neonates had low birth weight which was related to the finding of study investigated by Sushmitha ES *et al* [1] where 46.53% neonates had low birth weight.

In our study, 52.72% of neonates were 1 day old, whereas 35.45% were 2 to 7 days old. Together with morphological and physiological differences from older neonates, they made up around 88.17% of all infants with iatrogenic skin damage, which obviously rendered the group more vulnerable. These findings concurred with those of Sushmitha ES *et al* [1], who found that 47.52% of the patients were infants, and 39.50% were between 2 and 7 days old.

Needleprick injuries were the most frequently reported iatrogenic injury in 84 (76.36%) of 110 newborns followed by adhesive tape injuries (22.72%), diaper dermatitis (13.63%), thermal injuries (10.90%), bronze baby syndrome (4.54%), CPAP injuries (4.54%), perinatal injuries (3.63%) and extravasation injuries (2.72%). These results were comparable to study by Sushmitha ES *et al*,¹ where 70.34% showed needle prick injuries. Whereas in contrast to our study, adhesive tape injuries in Sushmitha ES *et al* [1] study were 0.85%.

In a study conducted by Sharma SK *et al* [9], 21.31% neonates showed adhesive tape injuries and 19.67% neonates showed diaper dermatitis, which were similar to findings of our study. In contrast to our study, 13.1% neonates showed extravasation injury in Sharma SK *et al* [9] study.

No matter how straightforward and routine the postpartum care may seem, the neonates undergo a number of procedures between their admission and discharge, including the insertion of catheters, capillary, venous, and arterial punctures, probes, placement of adhesive devices, use of sensors, placement of electrodes, body hygiene, dressing changes, and position changes, among others. All of these incidents contribute to the development of lesions because of how frequently they occur throughout the hospital stay [4-10].

Iatrogenic injuries are mainly classified into [11].

- 1) Iatrogenic disorders of newborn like scars
- 2) Iatrogenic injury during pregnancy like during amniocentesis and chorionic villous sampling
- 3) Iatrogenic injuries during labour like during foetal monitoring, instrumental delivery or caesarean section
- 4) Iatrogenic disorders after birth:
 - a) Damage produced while maintaining adequate respiration using ET tube and continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP)
 - b) Arterial catheterization
 - c) Extravasation injuries
 - d) Transcutaneous monitoring
 - e) Adhesive tape damage
 - f) Needle prick injuries
 - g) Vaccination

Neonatal jaundice is a prevalent condition in the first two weeks of life, and phototherapy is the most commonly used treatment. Bronze baby syndrome is a less common phototherapy consequence. The term "bronze baby syndrome" describes newborns receiving phototherapy for hyperbilirubinemia who have a grayish-brown coloring in their skin, serum, and urine. A combination of photoisomers of bilirubin, biliverdin, or a photoproduct of copper-porphyrin metabolism appear to be responsible for the condition, which normally manifests 1–7 days after the commencement of phototherapy and progressively disappears over several weeks after phototherapy is stopped [12].

Bronze infant syndrome normally does not require treatment because the pigmentation gradually fades after phototherapy is discontinued [13].

Measures to prevent iatrogenic injuries

Maintaining basic skin care in premature infants prevents many iatrogenic injuries. It mainly consists of –

1. Use adhesives sparingly:
Put on a protective dressing where you often tape (endotracheal & nasogastric tube placement). Use non-adhesive electrodes and only replace them when they stop working.
2. Limit bathing:
Wait until body temperature has settled before beginning first cleaning. Don't use cleaning products for the first two weeks. In a humid atmosphere, use warm water and damp cotton pledgets. No more than twice a week should be spent on surface cleaning. Use short-contact chlorhexidine for skin preparation if antimicrobial protection is necessary (except on the face).
3. Beware of content and quality of all topically applied agents:
These include perineal products, diaper wipes, adhesive removers, and antibacterial cleansers. If at all feasible, dispense from single-use containers.
4. Consider use of ointment, emollient for xerosis or minor skin abrasions. Guard against excessive thermal and UV-exposure:
Use Plexiglas shielding over day lightfluorescent phototherapy.
5. Protect sites of cutaneous injury with suitable occlusive dressing:

Apply a film dressing to places that don't exude. If a wound is exuding, apply a foam dressing. Maintain the proper level of moisture where the skin and clothing meet. With each change of the dressing, remove the necrotic debris [14].

Each piece of tape or adhesive should be thoroughly checked before use, especially if it will be placed on the baby's skin, to prevent damage from adhesives. A pectin-based skin barrier, such as the sort used for

ostomy care, can be utilized to protect skin. The baby's skin is topically covered with this in all locations where tape will be utilized [15]. Using karaya gum electrodes, which have been demonstrated to be mild on delicate skin, very easy to remove or replace, and adequately monitor the cardiorespiratory system, is another method of reducing skin damage from adhesives. To inspect the skin underneath and avoid any silver chloride gel harm, these electrodes should be removed and turned at least once every day [16]. Gently and carefully must be used when removing adhesive. Alcohol and/or adhesive removers should not be used often due to the potential for irritation and absorption. For gently soaking off adhesives, use gauze soaked in warm water. Only use alcohol or adhesive removers in an emergency situation or after the adhesives have melted and softened on the skin. If used, they must be removed with water [17].

Diaper dermatitis can be prevented by regular change of diapers and proper wiping off of faecal material. Iatrogenic injuries during labour can be prevented by careful use of instruments and proper handling of babies.

Conclusion

Neonatal dermatology is a topic that is perfect for research from a variety of options, including its clinical importance, ubiquitous Ness and protean manifestations. However, close communication between the dermatologist and pediatrician is crucial to enable early detection and treatment and reduce parental concern.

Skin injury can result from a number of neonatal iatrogenic injuries. To prevent unnecessary treatment of the delicate newborn skin, it is essential to recognize normal phenomena and distinguish them from more serious cutaneous disorders. Prompt diagnosis and treatment of serious disorders, as well as genetic counselling for parents in cases of congenital malformations and Geno dermatoses play vital role. Because of the scarcity of studies,

obstetricians, paediatricians, dermatologists, and nursing staff are less acquainted with these conditions. As a result, it is important to keep all medical professionals involved in infant care, up to date.

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